

Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies of Farmers to Climate Variability and Change in the Guinea Savanna Region of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Global climatic conditions are rapidly changing and therefore there is the urgent need to tackle them in real time. This study however is intended to assess farmer's awareness of climate change, as well as their mitigation and adaptation strategies. This was achieved using the proportionate and systematic sampling technique. A total of 372 questionnaires were administered to the respondents and only 333 were retrieved. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used to conduct a descriptive statistical analysis of the data. The result shows that 83.2% of the respondents were that climate was varying and their sources of information were 34.7% self observation, 18.2% from radio, 11.9% from friends while 13.2% from television. However, 38.5% of the respondent said climate variability was caused by God, 30.9% by greenhouse gases, while 25.3% and 10.4% were caused by deforestation and urbanization. 37.2% received fertilizer from government and non – government organization to boost soil fertility as a mitigation strategy, 26.0% received monetary assistance, 18.8% received trainings and 18.1% improved seeds while 62.6% of farmers adopted early planting as an adaptation strategy, 82.1% late planting,, 75.6% planting early maturing plants, 72.8% planting disease and pest resistant crops and 87.4% relocates to new sites among others. The study recommended the involvement of farmers as stakeholders in the debate and implementation of climate change policies, encourage irrigation farming and agricultural mechanization and increase the funding of climate related agencies among others.

Key Words: Mitigation, Adaptation, Climate Change, Farmers, Guinea savanna

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a ubiquitous Phenomenon having a wide range of implications and constitutes one of the 21st Century key challenges to development the world over, United Nation Development Programme (UNDP, 2007). Climate change is caused by factors such as biotic processes, variations in solar radiation received by the earth, plate tectonics and volcanic eruptions. Certain human activities have also been identified as significant causes of recent climate change often referred to as Global warming. There is now a strong consensus that climate change presents an urgent challenge to human welfare and sustainable development, (Ayansina and Ogunbo (2009). Global warming is the increase in the average temperature of the earth's near surface air and oceans, since the mid twentieth century and its projected continuation, the scientific community has reached a consensus that

global warming is real and that human activities are causing the warming trend. Global temperature has steadily risen over the last century and has been estimated that average global temperature of the earth surface increased by $0.74 \pm 0.80^{\circ}\text{C}$ recently summarized by the Intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC) indicate that global surface temperature will rise further by 1.1°C to 6.4°C during the 21st century, (http://en.Wikipedia.org/wiki/global_warming).

According to Ayansina et al (2009), climate change is already having a significant impact on economics and communities. Rising average temperature do not necessarily means balmer winters. Some regions will experience more extreme heat while others cool slightly. Floods, drought and intense summer heat could result in violent storms and other extreme weather events could also result from the increased energy stored in our warming atmosphere. One of the most serious impacts of climate change is how it will affect water resources. The knowledge of climate variability over the period of instrumental records and beyond on temporal and spatial scale is important to understand the nature of different climate systems and their impact on the environment and society, (Oguntunde, Abiodun and Lischied, 2012). Most of the observational and numerical simulation studies on climate are based on the instrumental records of about a century which are aimed at understanding of the natural variability. This is essential if we are predicting global and regional climate variations, determine the extent of human influence on the climate and make sound projections of human induced climate change. The climate of allocation can be understood mostly in terms of annual and seasonal averages of temperature and precipitation. The global climate has change rapidly with global mean temperature increasing by 0.7°C within the last century, Inter – governmental partnership on climate change IPCC, 2007). However, the rates of change are significantly different among regions (IPCC, 2007). This is primarily due to the varied types of land surfaces with different surface albedo, evapotranspiration and carbon cycle affecting the climate in different ways (Meissner, Weaver, Mathews and Cox, 2003; Synder, Delire and Foley, 2004).

Mitigation however, is a means through which causes of climate change can be curbed, it is about reducing human activities that intensifies the emission of the gases which perpetuate global warming. It implies the innovation of technologies and energy sources that are not detrimental to the ecosystem health, transition of environmentally unfriendly practices, efficient use of resources and perhaps effective policy and governance. It require bottom to top approach and vice – versa. Sharma and Kunar (1998) and Kates (2000) among others, states that greater consideration has been given to climate change mitigation than to adaptation measures. The multi dimensional mitigation methodology is aimed at

achieving a low – carbon society. According to IPCC (2007), some mitigation practices that can be employed are use of renewable heat and power (Hydro Power, Solar, Wind and Bio Energy), non – motorized transport e.g. walking and cycling, improved cooking stoves, alternative refrigeration fluids to reduce deforestation, improved crop and grazing land management etc. Other measures that can be taken up as mitigation practices include: waste recycling and afforestation.

While adaptation is simply an attempt to limit susceptibility to climate change impact, According to Ngigi (in Ogbo et al 2012) Adaptation involves the action that people takes in response to or in anticipation of, projected or actual change. It is a method of dealing with the symptoms of to reduce the vulnerability of the ecosystem to climate change and not the underlying causative factors. Basically adaptation is a means by which individuals lessens the negative effective of climate variation on their wellbeing. It helps to shrink the susceptibility of the ecosystem to the impact of climate change. According to Onokerhoraye 2011: 4) adaptation to climate is a response to climate change that seeks to reduce vulnerability of natural and human systems to climate effects. The need to adapt to the variability of climate is a basic one as supported by Nwafor (2007) argued that the biting effect of climate change will be felt more in developing countries, particularly in Africa due to their limited resources and low adaptive capacity. It is important states, organizations and individuals engage new methods of living that has positive impact on climate. The adoption of adaptation strategies is most important for developing countries including Nigeria as the also suffer the impact of climate variation that has serious implication for socio – economic development, thus agreeing with Odjugo and Ikhuoria(2003) who revealed that Nigeria is already being plagued with diverse ecological problems, which can be linked to the current global climate change. Slobodan (2012) also suggested that adaptive capacity is closely linked to social and economic development. Little wonder develop countries are able to adapt more succinctly.

Studies by Osunsina, Oduntan, Oladiran and Moyaki (2019), Ogunbode, Ogunbible, Odekunle and Asifat (2019 and Odjugo (2013) among others, revealed that majority of people in Nigeria are unaware of climate change and adaptive measures to cope with same, despite their high vulnerability to the impacts. In other scenarios, people may be aware of climate change but lack knowledge of effective adaptive strategies. The low level of public awareness of climate change across sub – Saharan African countries could be ascribed to the fact African countries are over whelmed with numerous problems ranging from

poverty to political conflicts, hence climate change is not seen as a priority (UNFCCC, 2007; UNDP, 2007)

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area

The Guinea Savanna is located in the middle of Nigeria and is the most extensive ecological zone. It is divided into two parts namely; Northern and Southern Guinea Savanna. The Guinea savanna extends from Ondo, Edo, Anambra and Enugu States in the south through Oyo State to Kwara State, Kogi State, Benue State, Nasarawa State, Niger State, Plateau State and Kaduna. It lies between latitude 7° and 12°N and longitude 4° and 15°E. However, the three States of Plateau, Nasarawa and Benue selected for this study are bounded by Bauchi State in the northeast, Taraba State in east, Enugu and Cross River states in the south, Kaduna and Federal Capital Territory in the northwest and Kogi in southwest (Ishaku 2019). The climate of the study area is largely influenced by the movement of trade winds, which are the West Africa Monsoon (the dry desiccating air mass emanating from the Sahara desert and the maritime air mass originating from the Atlantic Ocean). These two air masses meet at the inter-tropical convergence zone (I.T.C.Z) and it is the seasonal movement of these fronts that determine the climate of the area.

The guinea savanna region typically experiences wet and dry season from April to October and November to March respectively, the duration of the season varies from the south to the extreme north of the savanna. The dry season generally is shorter in the southern part of the savanna when compared to the northern part. Precipitation also decreases northwards; this is because some southern part of the guinea savanna region enjoys double maxima of rainfall, while the northern part experiences single maxima of rainfall. Mean annual rainfall in the region ranges from 720.1mm and 1430.1mm (Oladipo, 1995). Its climate is of the tropical wet and dry type (Aw – Koppen Classification) with oscillation in climatic elements which are believed to have occurred in the past (Ayoade, 2004). Temperature is generally high in the savanna region; this is partly due to the fact that the region lies within the tropics where the apparent movement of the sun is limited. Secondly there is a noticeable spatial temporal variation in temperature within the guinea savanna region. The highlands and plateaus for instance the Jos – plateaus records mean annual temperature of between 21°C to 25°C, while the plain generally have a mean annual temperature of about 27°C. The rainy season brings in low temperature because of the influence of cloud cover and the cooling effect of the rains especially in July and August when the savanna regions tend to receive its highest rainfall. Temperature picks up in September increasing through to November and dropping

again in December/ January because of the harmattan winds. The warmest temperature usually occurs in the dry season in the months of March and April, though this has changed drastically in the recent times with the warmness stretching further than April as is the case in Jos now. Relative humidity fluctuates between a low of 20% in January to a high of 80% in August. The unique physical features of the guinea savanna are its high relief especially in the north, where the Jos – plateaux is among the prominent. Soil properties vary in spatial and temporal dimension (Sokout, *et al*/ 2011) and such variations depict systematic changes as functions of geology and derived lands forms

Figure1: Nigeria Showing Selected Study States (Plateau, Nasarawa and (Benue) in the Guinea Savanna Region.

Methods of Data Collection

The study applied the multi – stage systematic sampling technique to collect the primary data where three states of Plateau, Nasarawa and Benue were selected. In Plateau State three local government areas of Bassa, Bokkos and Shendam were selected, in Nasarawa State, Keffi, Nasarawa – Eggon and Doma were selected, while in Benue State, Konshisha, Otukpo and Tarka were selected. Furthermore, four

localities were selected from each of the nine local government areas of the three states in the study areas (see table 1 below). However, questionnaires were administered systematically to respondents in the study area through the help of field assistants. The study in Plateau State in administering the questionnaire three houses were counted and the administration done to a respondent in the fourth house, in Nasarawa State four houses were counted and the questionnaire administered to a respondent in the fifth house while in Benue State nine houses were counted and a questionnaire was administered to a respondent in the tenth house. The systematic variation in the administration of the questionnaires was with respect to the difference in the number of respondents in the three states. In order to achieve the stipulated objective of the study data on farmers' mitigation and adaptation strategies were collected and analyzed descriptively using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version twenty two (22)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Socio-economic and demographic characteristics of respondents

The result presented in Table1 shows the socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the respondents. The results shows the respondents selected in the three states ; in Plateau State 22.9% of the respondents were interviewed, in Nasarawa State 27.3% were interviewed, while in Benue State 52.1% of the respondents were interviewed. Most (24.0 %) of the respondents were within age group 41 and above, this means that the respondents in the study area were old enough to attest to the fact of the existence or not of the phenomenon of temperature and rainfall variability and how it has impacted on their crop yield within the study period. Most (62.4%) of the respondents were males and the remaining 37.6% were female. This implies that majority of the farmers in the study area were male and were within the active age for farming. Also 51.7% of the respondents were married, 29% were single, 9.9% were widows, while 6.6% and 3.35 were separated and divorced respectively. Their marital status shows that most of these respondents have families they were responsible to and therefore will need more resources and food to take care of them.

However, 31.4% of the respondents had primary education, 30.6% had secondary education, 17.4% had tertiary education while 18.2% and 22.0% respectively had no formal and other forms of education implying that most of them were not very educated.

Table1: Socio-economic and demographic characteristics of respondents.

Variable	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Benue	Konshisha	47	24.9
	Tarka	43	22.8
	Otukpo	99	52.4
	Total	189	100
Nasarawa	Keffi	33	33.3
	Nasarawa – Eggon	39	39.4
	Doma	27	27.3
	Total	99	100
Plateau	Bassa	20	24.1
	Bokkos	43	51.8
	Shendam	20	24.1
	Total	83	100
Age	21 – 25	61	16.8
	26 – 30	64	17.6
	31 – 35	71	19.6
	36 – 40	80	22.0
	41 and above	87	24.0
	Total	363	100
Sex	Male	226	62.4
	Female	137	37.6
	Total	363	100
Marital status	Single	105	29.0
	Married	187	51.7
	Widow	36	9.9
	Separated	24	6.6
	Divorced	11	3.0
	Total	363	100
Educational status	Primary	114	31.4
	Secondary	111	30.6
	Tertiary	63	17.4
	No – formal	66	18.2
	Other	9	2.2
	Total	363	100
Other occupation aside farming	Civil servant	91	25.1
	Business	161	44.4
	Artisan	53	14.6
	Others	58	16.0
	Total	363	100
Years of farming experience	5 – 10	13	3.6
	15 – 20	26	7.2
	25 – 30	47	12.9
	35 – 40	122	33.6

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45 & above	154	42.4
Total	363	100

Source: Author's field work 2018

This could probably be due to the fact that they were rural dwellers and may not have access to good schooling facilities or even the capacity to further their education. Almost half (44.4%) of the respondents were do business aside farming, 25.1% were civil servant, 14.6% were artisans, while 16.0% engaged in other forms of livelihood, meaning that not the respondents were purely farmers. On the years of farming experience, about half (42.4%) of the farmers had between 45 and above years of farming experience, this is an indication that the respondents were experienced enough to respond to the issues relating to climate variability and change as it relates to the adaptation and mitigation strategies they employed in their communities. Agriculture stands to be greatly affected by the vagaries of weather and climate. However, modifying current management of agricultural systems could therefore greatly help to mitigate global anthropogenic emissions that affects crop yields, Table 2 shows the various strategies adopted by respondents as their ways of ameliorating the effects of climate variability and change. However, the result shows that majority (79.3%) of the respondents got different form of assistance as a measure of helping them mitigate upon the effect of climate variability. Many (37.2%) of the respondents were given fertilizer assistance various governments and non – profit organizations, 26.0% received monetary assistance, while 18.8% and 18 received trainings and improved seeds. However, 39.2% of this assistance came from the state governments, 33.7% from the local governments, while 13.9% and 13.2% came from the federal government and private donors.

Mitigation strategies of respondents to Climate Variability and Change

Table2: Mitigation strategies of respondents to Climate Variability and Change

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Assistance towards mitigating Climate variability	Yes	288	79.3
	No	75	20.7
	Total	363	100
Types of assistance	Monetary	75	26.0
	Improved seeds	52	18.1
	Fertilizer	107	37.2
	Trainings	54	18.8
Source of assistance	Federal government	40	13.9
	State government	113	39.2
	Local government	97	33.7
	Private donors	38	13.2
Fertilizer use	Yes	262	91.0

No	26	9.0
Domestic	191	66.4
Commercial	97	33.6

Source: author's field work 2018

Most of this assistance came from the state and local government perhaps because it is the closest government to the people. More than half (91.0%) of the respondents use fertilizer as a measure of mitigating against the effect of climate variability, while (68.4%) of them used food storage as a measure of mitigating against future shortages so as to cope with the effect of climate variability.

Adaptation strategies of respondents to climate variability and Change

Table 3: Adaptation strategies of respondents to climate variability and Change

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Practiced of adaptation	Yes	246	67.8
	No	117	32.2
	Total	363	100
Planting early	Yes	154	62.7
	No	92	37.4
Planting lately	Yes	202	82.1
	No	44	17.9
Planting early maturing crops	Yes	186	75.6
	No	60	24.4
Planting disease and pest resistant crops	Yes	179	72.8
	No	67	27.2
Relocation to new sites	Yes	215	87.4
	No	31	12.6
Fertilizer usage	Yes	180	73.2
	No	66	26.8
Processing of crops	Yes	195	79.3
	No	51	20.7
Planting cover crops	Yes	189	76.9
	No	57	23.2
Application of herbicides	Yes	170	69.1
	No	76	30.9

Source: Author's field work 2018.

Climate variability and change are among the most important challenges facing least developed countries because of their strong reliance on rain fed agriculture. However, with the changes in precipitation pattern, temperature, length growing season and frequency of extreme weather events, considerable effort would be

required to prepare developing nations to deal with this climate related impacts on agriculture. Adaptation in agriculture is a norm, since farmers had always had to adapt to the vagaries of weather and climate on weekly, monthly, seasonal annual and on large time scales. Adaptation strategies vary with agricultural system, location and scenarios of climate variability. According to table 4:22, 67.8% of the respondents indicated they took adaptation measures and had implemented at least one in the past, and some of these adaptation measures included; soil and water conservation and agronomic practices such as crop rotation, inter - - cropping, adjusting planting dates, diversifying crop types, use of fertilizers, use of improved crop varieties, application of manure and irrigation practices (FAO, 2007).

However, 62.6% of the farmers in this study said they adopted early planting of crops as a measure of adapting to the effect of climate variability, 82.1% of the respondents late planting, 75.6% the planting of early maturing crops, agreeing with the results of Jidauna (2016) who observed that 65.5% of respondents in Rano and Bebeji also adopted planting of early maturing crops as a measure of adapting to climate variability, while 72.8% adopted the planting of disease resistant varieties of crops also agreeing with Jidauna in 2016 who found that 60.8% of respondents in Kura and Bunkure adopted the use of disease and pest resistant crops as a measure of adaptation, example of disease resistant variety of maize in Nigeria are; Western yellow, DMR – LSRV and ZPBSR, that of rice are ; FARO 44, FARO 52, FARO 63 and UPIA 2(WAR), while that sorghum are; SAMSORG 47 (Local name ZAUNA INUWA, SAMSORG 48 (KAURA BORNNU). Furthermore, 87.4% of the respondents also adapted relocation to new sites as the appropriate measure of adapting to the variability of climate, 73.2% the use of fertilizer so as to improve on the fertility of the soil, 76.3% processing of crops so as to reduce spoilage and improve on availability of supply, while 76.9% and 69.1% the planting of cover crops and the application of herbicides as a measures of adapting to climate variability by reducing losses and enhancing productivity. Generally, the results reveal that the farmers had devised various ways to reduce the effects of climate variability on their production of crops over the period under which this study was conducted.

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